

Women and Education

Ms. Ranjita Ramesh Kalebere,^{1*} and Dr. Sopan Govind Khade²

¹PhD scholar, Department of Education, Shivaji University Kolhapur 416004 Maharashtra, India

²Assistant Professor, Vasant College of Education Urun-Islampur Dist. Sangli 415409 Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author E-mail: kranjita1445@gmail.com

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Abstract

Education is a milestone of women's empowerment because it helps them to respond to the challenges. It can help them confront their traditional role and change their lives according to their needs. Women's education is a fundamental human right. It remains a significant challenge in many parts of the world there are many barriers in providing equal and quality education for women. *Early marriage and pregnancy*, Child labor, Malnutrition, Lack of access to educational facilities, Lack of inclusive and quality learning environment, Sanitation and menstrual problems, Societal and Cultural Barriers, Gender stereotypes, Lack of female role models, Economic Challenges, Inequality in access, Gender-biased curriculum, Sexual harassment, Lack of female teachers. Health Issues are some of the hindrances in developing women's education. Various reforms and initiatives are taken by the Indian government to bring women's education to an equal level. It is time to focus thoroughly on women's education for the development of our country.

Introduction

Education is an effective medium to develop ourselves to achieve something special in life. In every human's life, education is an effective tool in decreasing the difficulties. The knowledge obtained through education encourages everybody to face all types of problems throughout their life. To achieve real success in life, and to improve career growth, education is a medium to open various doors of opportunities. Education can make a big impact on anyone's life.

There are so many ways to boost the status of education. Education plays an important role in everybody's life in this modern era. In this challenging life, everyone must have got proper and quality education to achieve the goals of life. Education does not only help for a good job but also develops the ability to face the problems in life with a new perspective.

Objectives of paper

1. To delineate the problems in education faced by women in India.
2. To elucidate the changing role of women in a new era.

Research Methodology of this paper

The presented research paper is based on secondary sources. For this, observation, various reference texts, articles, and secondary sources like internet sources have been used and content analysis techniques have been used.

Importance of education for human wellbeing

Education is more than just acquiring knowledge for both men and women it is important to have quality education because education contributes to personal fulfillment and happiness. For the creation of a strong and modern society Education is the most important part which performs the best part in the development and improvement of the nation. It is not merely a personal benefit; it's a powerful tool for societal transformation. It is an essential way to deliver a bright future. The citizens of the nation are responsible for a healthier future for them it's a cornerstone for building a fulfilling and prosperous life. It helps empower women, leading to better maternal and child health. Education is considered the most important part of empowering women in society. Education plays an important role in the cultural, economic, political, and social, development of society. It is also important for developing the personality of an individual.

A good and quality education provides many purposes to life like fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills, building confidence and self-esteem, and Lifelong Learning and Personal Growth.

Education cultivates curiosity and a thirst for knowledge it is essential for an individual's personality development, increase in social standard, the progress of social well-being, and financial position. To develop the nation, and establish a purpose for life education provides strength informs us of many social afflictions, and helps to find out the best remedies for any problems related to life.

Education gives the sensibility it can also help to solve social challenges such as poverty, inequality, and population. It is an effective way to understand all human responsibilities. Education has the complete strength to develop a country in a specific way. By investing in education, we invest in a healthier, more equitable, and sustainable future for all.

Importance of women's education

"If you educate a man, you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman, you educate a whole family, women empowered means mother India empowered", (Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru). Women's education is crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It's a powerful tool for breaking the cycle of poverty, improving health outcomes, and building stronger, more equitable societies. Investing in women's education is an investment in the bright future of the nation. In India, women's education is a cornerstone for the progress and development of the country. It's not only just about empowering individuals but also helps in improving the life standard of women at home and outside.

A well-educated woman has better job opportunities, higher earning potential, and can contribute significantly to their family and community. Educated women

Provides the skills, knowledge, quality work, and self-assurance about her work confidently. A well-educated woman can contribute to stronger families and communities. Educated women are more likely to be productive and well-organized at work.

Educated women can help to promote the education of their girl children, challenge gender stereotypes, and advocate for women's rights. Educated women can take decisions about their health and that of their families, leading to improved maternal and child health. They can also help in the reduction of the infant mortality rate and the growth of the population.

Capabilities of women in changing the scenario of education

Women have the capabilities to drive positive change across various sectors including education. Women's unique perspectives, experiences, and skills have the potential to reshape the educational scenario. Women educators can contribute to creating a positive and supportive school culture where students feel safe, respected, and valued.

Women are always capable of understanding and responding to the emotional needs of students. They can foster a supportive learning environment where students feel valued and encouraged. Women often demonstrate exceptional abilities in building support with students. They can effectively communicate with colleagues, and parents, fostering collaboration and trust between each other. They have the unique ability to create learning environments that will help empower all students to reach their full potential. Women educators can work as a powerful role model for young girls. They can guide female students by inspiring them to pursue their dreams and break gender stereotypes. They also guide in mentoring and supporting both male and female students.

Women can bring fresh techniques and innovative approaches to teaching and learning. They can also develop creative strategies to engage students and make education more relevant and enjoyable. Women often demonstrate a strong commitment to lifelong learning and professional development. They are adaptable to changing educational trends and technologies to provide the best possible education for their students.

Women are often connected with communities and can effectively communicate with parents to support student success. Research shows that women educators can positively impact student achievement, particularly for girls.

Women are always at the forefront of initiatives to increase access to education for marginalized groups, including students with disabilities, girls, and those from low-income communities. Women educators can play a crucial role in developing inclusive education.

By supporting the unique capabilities of women, education systems can become more inclusive, and effective in preparing students for success to face new social challenges.

Problems of Women's Education in India

Women's education is a basic human right. It remains a significant challenge in many parts of the world. Here are some of the primary problems associated with women's education:

- **Early marriage and pregnancy**– Girls are married at an early age. Pregnancy also happens too early. They are facing various health-related issues due to early pregnancy. The girls are unable to take care of themselves.
- **Child labor** –Illegally children are working at tea stalls and small hotels for serving and cleaning purposes. Girls are often drop out from school to help to household income. They are unable to join a school or study. Uneducated Families believe in educating boys instead of girls.
- **Poverty**– Girl child education often faces financial problems. There are many factors preventing girls from going to school. Lack of financial resources at home, Families may prioritize educating male children due to financial constraints. Taking care of younger brothers or sisters, and doing household work are some reasons in front of women.
- **Malnutrition**: Poor nutrition can impact girls' cognitive development and ability to learn, which directly makes a huge impact on the future of the society and nation
- **Lack of access to educational facilities**: Lack of school infrastructure, and transport facilities. This is particularly prevalent in rural areas.
- **Lack of inclusive and quality learning environments**: Lack of inclusive and quality learning
- **Experiences throughout the syllabus**: A male-dominated curriculum creates hindrances in the overall development of women not given proper opportunities.

- **Sanitation and menstrual problems** –Lack of sanitation facilities at school is one of the main social problems related to women's education. Most of the girls choose to drop out of school due to a lack of access to a proper bathroom or privacy during menstruation. Lack of menstrual hygiene facilities can affect girls' attendance and performance.
- **Societal and Cultural Barriers:** local conditions, social and cultural rituals, and conditions create barriers to the education of women.
- **Gender stereotypes:** Girls are normally inferior to boys and should prioritize domestic duties over education.
- **Cultural norms:** In some cultures, women are expected to stay home to take care of their family. This limits their educational opportunities.
- **Lack of female role models:** The absence of successful women in educational or professional fields can discourage girls from pursuing higher education.
- **Economic Challenges:** poverty, and lack of study materials due to financial problems.
- **Inequality in access:** Girls, especially in developing countries, have limited access to schools and educational resources.
- **Gender-biased curriculum:** Textbooks and teaching materials often reinforce gender stereotypes.
- **Sexual harassment:** Girls face a higher risk of sexual harassment in schools, deterring them from attending.
- **Lack of female teachers:** The absence of female role models in the teaching profession can negatively impact girls' education.
- **Health Issues:** Health Issues due to lack of awareness about nutritious food.
- **Teenage pregnancy:** Due to this problem girls drop out of school.

Parental attitude, socio-economic condition of parents, lack of finance, lack of security, lack of infrastructure at school, and superstitions related to girls, are the major challenges for promoting girls' education in India.

Remedies to overcome the problem

Overcoming these challenges requires working with communities. By involving governments and individuals some strategies can be developed:

- Promoting gender equality: Challenging gender equality and promoting girls' rights.
- Investing in education: Providing free and compulsory education and proper study material for all girls.
- Improving school infrastructure: Ensuring a safe and accessible school environment and sanitation facilities for girls.
- Empowering women: Supporting women's leadership to create lady role models and participation in decision-making.
- Raising awareness: Educating communities about the importance of girls' education.

Recent Trends in Women's Education

Women's education has seen significant development in recent years, with several key trends emerging:

- **Rising enrollment rates:** due to various efforts it is witnessed that more girls and women are enrolling in schools and universities worldwide.
- **Focus on marginalized groups:** Efforts are being made to bring girls and in rural, impoverished, and conflict-affected areas into the mainstream of education.
- **Digital learning:** Online platforms are proving very useful and important access to education for women, especially in remote regions.

- **Emphasis on Quality Education and Improved Teaching Methods:** Innovative teaching approaches and techniques are being adopted to address female students for the betterment of education.
- **STEM education:** Promoting girls' interest in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
- **Lifelong learning:** Encouraging continued education and skill development for women
- **Addressing Gender-Based Challenges and Safe learning environments:** Combating sexual harassment and violence in schools and universities.
- **Mentorship and leadership programs:** Empowering women to take on leadership roles and providing various opportunities for leadership
- **Addressing gender stereotypes:** Challenging harmful gender norms through education and treating girls and women equally with men.
- **Economic Empowerment through Vocational training:** Equipping women with skills for employment for self-dependency.
- **Entrepreneurship education:** Supporting women-owned businesses, providing special grants for women-owned businesses.
- **Financial literacy programs:** Helping women manage their financial condition and enable themselves to complete their financial needs by their own efforts.
- **Technology and Innovation Digital literacy:** Teaching women how to use technology effectively for the betterment of their lives.
- **AI and machine learning:** Exploring the potential of Artificial Intelligence to improve women's education.
- **Emphasis on higher education:** Increasing number of women pursuing higher degrees. Addressing gender gaps: Efforts to close the gender gap in STEM and many other fields.

Conclusion

Women's education gives power to equality. It also helps women to voice out their opinions. Women will be able to prevent themselves from dramatic situations. Women can become capable of looking after themselves and their families. Women can prove themselves in various sectors. Educated women can exclaim many social discrepancies. Including them into many sectors powerful system might be established. Lack of social awareness, superstitions, absence of adequate infrastructures, issue of coeducation, issue of inclusive education, and financial problems are some issues faced by women with their schooling in India.

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